

Deliverable D6.4

Report on global resources suitable for inclusion into the GDI

Project Title Grant agreement no	Genomic Data Infrastructure Grant agreement 101081813		
Project Acronym (EC Call)	GDI		
WP No & Title	WP6: Data Management		
WP Leaders	Rob Hooft (21. HRI)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	6.1. University of Helsinki		
Contractual delivery date	31/10/2025	Actual delivery date	31/10/2025
Delayed	[No]		
Partner(s) contributing to deliverable	UH		
Authors	Markus Perola (UH)		
Contributors	Tero Hiekkalinna (UH)		
Acknowledgements	Vilho Heikkinen (UH)		
Reviewers	Janis Klovins (LV), Hedi Peterson (EE)		

Log of changes

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
2/10/2025		Markus Perola (UH)	
31/10/2025		Tero Hiekkalinna (UH)	

The GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

Table of contents

Contents

1. Executive Summary	3
2. Contribution towards project outcomes	4
3. Methods	6
4. Description of work accomplished	6
4.1 Work Conducted	7
4.1.1 Identification of Resources	7
4.1.2 Interaction with Other WPs	7
4.1.3 Reliance on External Projects and Partners	8
4.2 Problems Encountered and Solutions	8
4.3 Summary	9
5. Results	9
5.1 Details of the Aggregate findings	9
5.2 Observations on Data Usability	10
5.3 Immediate Implications of the Results	10
6. Discussion	10
7. Conclusions & Impact	12
8. Next steps	13

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable (D6.4) extends the previous work conducted in Deliverable 6.2, which focused on European genomic resources, to a global scope. The aim was to systematically identify and describe global whole genome sequencing (WGS) resources and related datasets suitable for inclusion into the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI).

Unlike D6.2, which was based primarily on questionnaire responses, this work was carried out through a structured and comprehensive search of publicly available information, scientific literature, and online resources.

We identified globally 67 projects across multiple continents. Together, these projects represent about 22 million individuals with genomic data (GWAS/exome/WGS).

The findings highlight the immense scale of genomic data resources worldwide and their potential to enrich the European 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG) initiative with greater diversity and statistical power.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers</p>	No

The GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

(e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.	
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	No

3. Methods

Deliverable scope

The goal of D6.4 was to identify, classify, and quantify global WGS and related resources relevant for inclusion into GDI. By covering non-European projects, the work extends the diversity of represented populations and offers opportunities for large-scale federated analysis beyond Europe.

Methodology

The mapping exercise, conducted between October 2024 and August 2025, was based on:

- Literature searches in PubMed and Google Scholar for large-scale WGS, exome, and GWAS initiatives.
- Internet searches of known genomic consortia, cohort websites, and biobank repositories.
- Cross-validation with publicly accessible databases and national biobank portals.
- Inclusion criteria: datasets with significant sample sizes ($N > 100\,000$), relevance to population or disease-based genomics, and potential accessibility for research (such as open for collaboration at some level).
- Exclusion criteria: projects without genomic data, projects with inaccessible metadata, or initiatives too small in scale to be relevant for GDI.

This approach ensures broad coverage while maintaining reliability and professional transparency, in contrast to the direct questionnaire-based approach of D6.2.

Artificial intelligence tools (ChatGPT for example) were applied to extract information from selected target sites for inclusion in the metadata tables. All sample size information was verified by human cross-check for accuracy.

4. Description of work accomplished

This deliverable extends the previous work on European resources (D6.2¹) to a global scale. The mapping exercise was designed to systematically identify large-scale genomic resources across continents that could be relevant for inclusion into the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI). The work involved an intensive and structured search of online resources, scientific publications, and publicly available metadata.

The results of this work provide a consolidated view of international genomic initiatives, highlighting their scale, type of data, accessibility, and potential for integration with GDI.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887423>

4.1 Work Conducted

4.1.1 Identification of Resources

A systematic screening of major international consortia, national biobanks, and population-based cohorts was undertaken. This included:

- Searches of scientific literature and repositories.
- Targeted review of known large-scale initiatives such as 1000 Genomes, TOPMed, All of Us, UK Biobank, H3Africa, GenomeAsia, and national biobank projects across Asia-Pacific and Latin America.
- Extraction of structured metadata from official portals, reports, and published cohort descriptions.

AI was also used to cross-reference numerical data presented in this report and to support language editing in English.

4.1.2 Interaction with Other WPs

The work relied extensively on material and analyses produced by other Work Packages.

- WP1 (Coordination and Management): Provided overarching project documentation, which helped ensure that the global mapping exercise was aligned with the strategic objectives of GDI and the 1+MG initiative.
- WP2 (Technical Infrastructure): Delivered outputs on metadata standardisation, interoperability, and the compatibility of external resources with the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA) model. These materials informed the assessment of how global datasets could, in principle, be integrated into a federated framework.
- WP6 (Data Management): Earlier outputs, particularly Deliverable 6.2, served as the methodological baseline. The structure, classification of data types, and reporting conventions developed there were adopted and extended to the global level in D6.4.
- WP9 (Ethics and Legal): Documentation from WP9 was used as a reference for ethical and legal aspects, with particular relevance to cross-border data use. Their analyses of GDPR and jurisdictional differences provided the basis for evaluating the feasibility of including international datasets.

By relying on these outputs, D6.4 ensured consistency with the overall GDI framework while extending the mapping exercise beyond Europe.

We acknowledge the foundational work of these Work Packages, which made the present deliverable possible.

4.1.3 Reliance on External Projects and Partners

In addition to internal Work Packages, this deliverable relied on information, data, and documentation produced by several large international genomic initiatives. These resources provided valuable context and reference points for mapping global WGS datasets.

- All of Us (United States): Publicly available information on scale, recruitment strategies, and data access policies informed our understanding of how large, population-based cohorts outside Europe are organised and governed.
- TOPMed (United States): Publications and official project descriptions were used to quantify available WGS data and to evaluate the integration of phenotypic and clinical endpoints with genomic data.
- UK Biobank, Genomics England, and Our Future Health (United Kingdom): These projects provided well-documented models of large-scale sequencing in healthcare and research contexts. Their public documentation was used to estimate potential contributions to GDI, while acknowledging that the UK is not formally part of 1+MG.
- H3Africa (Pan-African initiative): Published reports and databases were reviewed to account for genomic resources in African populations, offering crucial diversity that is currently underrepresented in European cohorts.
- GenomeAsia100K and other Asian initiatives: Information from project portals and scientific articles provided insight into resources covering diverse Asian populations, which are essential for extending the global representation in GDI.
- International Cancer Genome Consortium (ICGC): Publicly available summaries of cancer sequencing datasets were used to assess disease-focused resources at the global level.

By systematically relying on the published outputs, portals, and data access frameworks of these initiatives, the work ensured that the global mapping exercise was comprehensive and representative, while avoiding assumptions about direct collaboration.

Again, we acknowledge the substantial efforts of these international projects, whose publicly available documentation made this mapping possible.

4.2 Problems Encountered and Solutions

Several challenges were encountered:

- Heterogeneity of reporting: Projects differ in how they present numbers of individuals, data types, and data accessibility. This was addressed by adopting a uniform classification system (WGS, Exome, GWAS) and conservative estimates when numbers were unclear.
- Incomplete or outdated information: Some project websites or publications did not contain current figures. To mitigate this, multiple independent sources were cross-checked, and where ambiguity remained, estimates were flagged.
- Access models: Many projects specify controlled or collaborative-only access, which complicates assessment of immediate usability within GDI. This was solved by classifying

The GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

access as open, controlled, or collaborative-only, without making assumptions about future negotiations.

- Overlap with European efforts: Certain projects are already included in European mapping. To avoid duplication, these were annotated as overlapping but still included in the global landscape description.

4.3 Summary

The work accomplished provides the first systematic overview of global genomic resources for potential integration into GDI. By collating metadata from 67 major projects covering ~22.4 million individuals, this deliverable demonstrates the scale and diversity of data available outside Europe. The work also highlights the challenges of heterogeneous reporting and access restrictions, but provides a structured baseline for future engagement with international partners.

5. Results

From the aggregated dataset (n=67 projects):

- Geographical coverage: Projects identified across North America, South America, Asia, Africa, and Oceania, in addition to major international initiatives.
- Individuals covered: ~22.4 million (GWAS/exome/WGS).
- Access models: Projects vary widely, from fully open-access (e.g. 1000 Genomes) to highly restricted collaborative frameworks (e.g. FinnGen, TOPMed).
- Phenotypic richness: Many resources integrate health record data, disease-specific endpoints, or demographic metadata, which enhances downstream usability.

Please see the attached Excel file² for the detailed mapping results, including project-level information on sample size, data type, access conditions, and phenotypic coverage. Not all the data retrieved is presented in this report but has been archived for future use and possible integration into project-level metadata registries.

5.1 Details of the Aggregate findings

- The majority of identified individuals with genomic data are linked to GWAS (~64% of the total), reflecting the long history and relative affordability of genotyping arrays compared to WGS.
- WGS datasets represent the fastest growing category, with over 4.8 million individuals included globally. Several ongoing initiatives (e.g., All of Us, Our Future Health, GenomeAsia100K) are expected to expand these numbers substantially in the coming years.
- Exome sequencing remains an important but smaller component (exomes in seven projects only), largely concentrated in disease-specific projects.

²<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1DzoD6KeMlbRZV1JPKMSTiRoqGzFeJ6zDP7mQtiGT4ig/edit?usp=sharing>

- Diversity is increasing, with major initiatives underway in Africa (H3Africa), Asia (GenomeAsia100K, Japanese Biobank projects), and Latin America (Mexico, Brazil), although these remain smaller in scale than North American and European efforts.

5.2 Observations on Data Usability

Data access was divided into three categories: open-access, controlled-access, or collaborative-only. However, in some cases, it was difficult to determine the category because the information was not stated clearly.

- Open-access datasets (e.g. 1000 Genomes, HGDP) remain critical for benchmarking but are limited in size.
- Controlled-access consortia (TOPMed, All of Us, UK Biobank) provide extremely rich resources but require structured application processes, often including collaborative agreements.
- Collaborative-only datasets (FinnGen, some national biobanks) represent significant potential but would require bilateral or multilateral agreements for access through GDI.
- Phenotypic depth is a distinguishing factor: many large-scale cohorts combine genomic data with electronic health records, longitudinal follow-up, and disease registries, increasing their scientific value but also adding complexity in terms of harmonisation and privacy regulation.

5.3 Immediate Implications of the Results

The aggregated mapping demonstrates that large volumes of high-quality genomic data already exist globally, often with associated phenotypic and health-related information. This reinforces the feasibility and value of extending GDI beyond European datasets. At the same time, it highlights the importance of:

- Developing common metadata standards to describe heterogeneous resources consistently.
- Establishing legal and ethical frameworks to enable responsible cross-border use.
- Prioritising diversity and representation, to ensure global findings benefit European healthcare and vice versa.

The combination of these factors makes the mapped global datasets highly relevant to the long-term ambitions of the 1+MG initiative and the European Genomic and Health Data Space. This will be discussed later in this Report.

6. Discussion

The global mapping exercise undertaken in this deliverable demonstrates both the remarkable scale of existing genomic resources and the breadth of their geographical and methodological diversity. With more than twenty-two million individuals represented across sixty-seven projects, it is evident that genomic data collection has become a truly worldwide effort, spanning North America, Europe, Asia, Africa, Latin America, and Oceania. What was once the domain of a handful of pioneering

The GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

initiatives has now evolved into a complex and interconnected landscape of large-scale population cohorts, disease-focused programmes, and international consortia.

A central finding is the strong growth of whole genome sequencing, now covering close to five million individuals worldwide. While genome-wide association studies (GWAS) still account for the majority of available data, the rapid expansion of WGS reflects falling sequencing costs and the increasing recognition of the value of comprehensive genome information. Importantly, a number of initiatives such as All of Us in the United States, GenomeAsia100K, and H3Africa are deliberately targeting populations that have historically been underrepresented in genomic research. This expansion has profound implications for the 1+MG initiative, as the availability of diverse genomic backgrounds strengthens both discovery potential and the generalisability of findings across populations.

The usability of these global resources is, however, uneven. A few projects, such as the 1000 Genomes Project and the Human Genome Diversity Project, provide fully open access but remain modest in size. At the other end of the spectrum, large and richly phenotyped cohorts such as TOPMed, All of Us, and UK Biobank require controlled access procedures and formal approvals. Some initiatives, including FinnGen, operate primarily on a collaborative-access model, where participation in the consortium is the main route to data use. These differences reflect both scientific and legal considerations, but they also pose challenges for integration into a federated framework such as GDI. It is clear that technical solutions alone will not be sufficient; structured agreements and governance mechanisms will also be required.

Ethical and legal issues are particularly salient in the global context. The European Union benefits from the harmonisation provided by the GDPR, but outside Europe there is a wide variety of regulatory environments. Questions of consent, data privacy, and international transfer are addressed in divergent ways across jurisdictions. Reliance on the analyses of WPG has underscored that interoperability in this domain will depend on building trust, negotiating recognition of standards, and finding workable compromises that respect both European and non-European legal frameworks. This is a non-trivial task but an essential one if global data are to be brought into the orbit of the 1+MG initiative. The Genomic Data Infrastructure project's harmonization and secure federated access are critical efforts focused on making vast, sensitive genomic and health datasets available for research and clinical use while maintaining privacy, security, and data sovereignty.

From the perspective of European research and healthcare, the benefits of drawing on global resources are considerable. Greater diversity enhances the robustness of genomic discoveries, increases statistical power for the detection of rare variants, and improves the portability of polygenic risk models. Access to independent international datasets also allows for validation of European findings and supports their translation into clinical practice. Beyond scientific considerations, engagement with global initiatives signals Europe's willingness to contribute to and benefit from worldwide collaborations in genomics, reinforcing the principles of equity and reciprocity in science.

At the same time, important challenges must not be underestimated. Harmonising technical standards across such heterogeneous datasets is a complex task, as is negotiating access in

The GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

environments where commercial interests or national priorities may constrain data sharing. Ensuring fair recognition and benefit-sharing with partners outside Europe is another critical concern. Finally, care must be taken to avoid duplicating efforts where other global infrastructures, such as GA4GH or ICGC, already provide established frameworks.

In summary, the results of this mapping exercise highlight both the opportunities and the challenges of incorporating global genomic resources into the GDI. The scale and diversity of available data represent an extraordinary opportunity to enrich the 1+MG initiative and strengthen the European Health Data Space. Realising this potential will, however, require careful coordination, sustained negotiation, and a commitment to ethical and equitable collaboration at the international level. This mapping exercise reveals the scale and heterogeneity of available genomic datasets. Unlike in Europe, where efforts are relatively coordinated through 1+MG and GoE, global datasets are dispersed across diverse initiatives with varying governance, access policies, and technical standards. However, this review was a one-time exercise; to ensure lasting impact, a permanent home for such a catalogue is needed. To be truly functional, the catalogue should operate as a two-way system, allowing cohorts with genomic data to upload their own metadata updates, provided that defined quality criteria are met. BBMRI-ERIC could be a suitable host.

7. Conclusions & Impact

This deliverable provides the first systematic account of global genomic resources that could, in principle, be aligned with the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI). By extending the work of Deliverable 6.2, which focused on European contributions, we have shown that the global landscape is both vast and rapidly evolving. The mapping identified sixty-seven major projects covering more than twenty-two million individuals, including nearly five million with whole genome sequencing data. These figures underscore the scale at which genomics is now being pursued internationally and illustrate the opportunities for Europe to situate its efforts within a truly global context.

The main conclusion is that the GDI and the 1+MG initiative stand to benefit greatly from strategic engagement with international datasets. Access to large, well-characterised cohorts such as TOPMed, All of Us, or UK Biobank would substantially increase statistical power and provide external validation opportunities for European discoveries. Equally important, the inclusion of initiatives from Africa, Asia, and Latin America would introduce much-needed diversity, ensuring that findings are not restricted to European populations but instead capture the global spectrum of genetic variation. Such diversity is essential for building equitable precision medicine tools that are relevant across ancestries. The results of this work will contribute valuable insights to other WPs, supporting sustainability planning and enhancing legal interoperability with jurisdictions outside the EU.

The impact of this work goes beyond research. Integrating global data into GDI would reinforce Europe's leadership in developing federated data infrastructures that respect privacy and legal boundaries while enabling large-scale analysis. It would also signal a clear commitment to reciprocity and inclusiveness in genomics, aligning European policy with the broader movement towards global health equity. For the European Health Data Space, these efforts open pathways to

The GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

link genomics with health records not only across Europe but in synergy with similar developments worldwide.

At the same time, the exercise has highlighted critical challenges that will shape the next steps. Technical issues such as metadata harmonisation and interoperability remain demanding but solvable within the federated model. More complex are the ethical and legal considerations of cross-border data use, which require sustained negotiation with international partners and careful alignment with European standards. Addressing these challenges will be essential to transform the mapped resources into practical assets for GDI.

In conclusion, the global mapping presented here provides a baseline for future work. It demonstrates the immense potential of integrating global genomic resources into the GDI while also making clear the need for coordinated solutions to technical, legal, and ethical barriers. If these challenges can be met, the result will be a more powerful, diverse, and inclusive data infrastructure that advances the goals of the 1+MG initiative and strengthens Europe's role in the global genomics community. The first systematic mapping of global WGS and related resources for potential integration into GDI. With nearly 5 million WGS samples globally and tens of millions of individuals with genomic and phenotypic data, there is a major opportunity to complement European resources.

The integration of these global datasets would strengthen the 1+MG initiative and position Europe as a key partner in worldwide genomic collaboration. By extending GDI beyond European borders, the initiative can contribute to global health equity, scientific discovery, and clinical innovation.

8. Next steps

The mapping of global genomic resources presented in this deliverable provides a foundation for future engagement and integration. The immediate next step will be to prioritise which international initiatives offer the most strategic value for the GDI and the 1+MG initiative. Large-scale programmes with established infrastructures, such as All of Us, TOPMed, UK Biobank, and Genomics England, represent obvious candidates. Equally important are initiatives in Africa, Asia, and Latin America, which bring diversity and global representation that European datasets alone cannot provide. Although it is challenging to estimate the exact amount of data that could be included in the GDI, any expansion should aim to encompass several hundred thousand entries from diverse populations. This would make the project even more valuable and engaging for everyone involved.

Moving forward, dialogue with international partners will be essential. This should begin with exploratory discussions to clarify mutual interests and constraints, particularly around data access models and governance. Parallel to this, technical pilots can be designed to test the feasibility of federated analyses across continental infrastructures, using synthetic or open-access datasets as initial testbeds.

Another priority will be to strengthen the ethical and legal frameworks that underpin global collaboration. Building on the work of WP9, specific attention should be given to models of reciprocity, consent management, and compliance with local regulations outside the EU. These

The GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

frameworks will need to balance respect for national sovereignty with the shared goal of advancing global health.

Finally, the insights gained here should feed into broader European initiatives, particularly the European Health Data Space. Linking global genomic resources to health record-based infrastructures in Europe will position GDI not only as a continental effort but as a node in an emerging global network for genomics and health.

The task ahead is ambitious, but the mapping carried out in this deliverable shows that the resources exist and the opportunities are real. With careful planning and sustained engagement, GDI can move from identifying global resources to making them part of a functioning, secure, and equitable data ecosystem to go further to utilize the work done in D6.4.

